

COVID-19 and Oogonia: Crafting a Genetic Time Bomb Through Barr Body Alterations

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In this article, I will present my personal point of view in three steps. First, I will talk about the famous electronic virus. Second, I will present my own interpretation of the potential role of the natural viruses. Third, I will finish with my expectations of what might hide beyond the current covid-19 pandemic.

1. The Electronic Virus

It is a malicious software (algorithm), created by the humans. It is inactive per se. However, when infiltrating within a functional software, it becomes active. It derives the infected software away from its predesignated function.

It might block the affected software, slow it down, or disable its effects. On a coronary, it can also speed up the affected software, and improve the process and the performance consequently. All depend upon the intentions of the human operating this virus. Unfortunately, the evil is always the product of this human actions.

2. The Natural Virus

It is almost the same as the electronic virus; however, is made by the nature itself. It consists of inactive genes (inactive software). It only becomes active in contact with a living cell. Then, the virus's genes will dominate the infected cell in order to copy itself a large number of times. Until this point, all scientists are in agreement.

2.1. A Misinterpretation

Since the human experienced fatigue, pain, and fever when infected by these viruses, he hence accused them of being pathogenic. However, the human himself knows a large number of non- pathogenic viruses, so what might he say about them?

2.2. A Big Question

If the software of the electronic virus can easily integrate within the host software, why can't the natural viruses do the same?

The natural viruses are much neater in their structure and more sophisticated than the electronic viruses. So logically, they must have the same ability to infiltrate and to integrate within the cell's genes.

2.3. The Unknown Soldiers

Personally, I do believe viruses to play more important roles in our lives than we used to think. Moreover, I do believe viruses deliver temporal updates as well as the environmental updates to the human cells. In turn, the living cells will receive these updates coming in form of viral genes, and integrate them into their original genetic code.

In other words, viruses are the messengers of Mother Nature to the humans to enable them to cope with the new circumstances. Sometimes, the contact between viruses and the human can be painful and quite evident. However, in the majority of cases, the contact between them runs smoothly and silently.

2.4. Tactical or Strategic Updates?

They are tactical if the target cells were the human somatic cells. Hence, the updates would affect some of the cell functions. They affect the person himself and do not have any consequence on his offspring.

However, they become strategic when the virus affects the male's spermatogonia and the female's oogonia in particular. Herein, the consequences will be more important influencing mainly the next generation. Actually, they can be extremely grave if the updates concern the oogonium cell itself. However, they can be more tolerable when they only affect the spermatogonium cell.

2.5. Negative or Positive Updates?

In general, the updates take care to enable the human to properly cope with the induced recent extracorporeal changes. Therefore, I expect them to be of positive impacts on the human life.

However, sometimes the changes' burden can be of great impact on the human health and/or the human function. Therefore, some of them are not without harmful side effects. I find it wise to evaluate each of these

updates separately. Some of these updates may be of great benefit, while others can be too devastating.

If the man used to be too aggressive toward the nature, why should the nature be generous in return? It is the harvest, as you saw you reap.

3. COVID-19

Coronavirus is one of the natural viruses. It follows the same regulations of action and of functions as well. However, due to its extreme virulence and aggression toward the human, I doubted its long-term, masked intentions towards the humanity. Actually, I wondered if it is just a virus to kill, or it hides something grave underneath all this terrible tragedy?

Personally, I do expect the worst to come later. This virus targets in reality the human essence, it targets the human genes themselves, particularly those of the spermatogonia and oogonia. The battle is still going on, and if the virus succeeds in infiltrating the nucleus of generative cells, then the consequences are going to be very difficult to predict.

3.1. If COVID-19 Only Infects Human Somatic Cells' Genes

Then, the updated changes will be tactical, only affect some of cell's functions. In this circumstance, the induced updates should have their impacts on the victim alone, and for the rest of his life. If they are good, which I deeply doubt in the case of Coronavirus, the victim will surely benefit. If they are negative, the patient will then suffer indefinitely.

3.2. If COVID-19 Only Infects Spermatogonia Genes

In this case, the induced changes will be strategic, almost of positive impacts on the descendants. When the oogonia remain save, the oocytes must remain save genetically. Healthy oocyte can play a major role in selecting the genetic modifications of male's sperms; approving the good updates and rejecting the negative ones.

[For more details about Spermatogenesis, refer to the linked video:](#)

3.3. If COVID-19 Also Infects Oogonia Genes

Herein, the catastrophe will be imminent. The virus might succeed modifying oogonia genes. Consequently, the resulting oocytes will be for

sure modified genetically. In such case, no one can predict the potential outcomes on the descendants of these genetically modified oocytes.

[For more details about Oocytogenesis, refer to the linked video:](#)

Usually, the oocyte controls the genes modifications in sperms. Upon fertilization, healthy oocyte selects the good genes' updates in sperms, while disapproves and rejects the harmful ones. Now, the oocytes themselves are affected by the virus. The harmful genes updates in a sperm can now freely pass to the offspring, and the good ones can do so as well.

For more details about the oocyte's role, read also my article:
[Eve Saved Human Identity, Adam Ensured Human Adaptation](#)

4. Barr Body: The Sentinel

I do believe the **Barr body** acts as the sentinel, which has protected and is still protecting the human identity. Moreover, I do believe Barr body remained unchanged since the time of the first woman, Eve. It has never changed in structure nor in functions since the dawn of humanity. Therefore, it will not be astonishing to find out identical Barr body, i.e. which has the same structure and functions, in all women.

Actually, Barr body always knows how to protect itself. In a female fetus, after a few numbers of cell divisions, it steps aside and is fortified in order to be protected from any potential extrinsic and intrinsic aggression.

[For more details about the Barr Body, refer to the linked video:](#)

Previously, Barr body has rejected the immune dyes used to study human cells microscopically. Thus, scientists have mistakenly accused it to be the inactive chromosome X. The concept which is conventionally accepted as Lyon hypothesis.

Personally, I do not agree with their consensus. I do believe Barr Body to be the only active female sexual chromosome. Moreover, I consider the second chromosome X as a porter of its partner in the chromosome pair XX. However, it is not a sexual chromosome per se.

4.1. Coronavirus Targets Barr body

However, I suspect COVID-19 is trying to reach Barr Body. If Coronavirus, or any other new virus to come in the future, succeeded in compromising the integrity of this body, we should hence fear of the worst to come regarding the identity of our existence as humans. The function as well as the appearance of nowadays human will not be the same after few generations, who knows?!

4.2. Look for Barr Body Modifications

These might be the indicator of Coronavirus victory, and that the virus has stormed the last fortress of the humanity; i.e. Barr Body. Therefore, Scientists should look for Barr body modifications in the somatic cells of the female neonates that are born during and/or after this pandemic. Any change in its form and/or in the structure must alert scientist of the imminent essential changes in the human race; in the function and maybe in its form as well.

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